

BuildingSmart Use-Case Definition – Simulation of Activities for the Digital Twin of a Construction Area by Collecting Automated Data to Have Higher Efficiency

Section 1: MetaData

1.1 Identification of the document

Title:

SIMULATION OF CONSTRUCTION ACTIVITIES USING DIGITAL TWIN CONSTRUCTION SITE DATA

ASHVIN: Assistants for Healthy, Safe and Productive Virtual Construction Design, Operation & Maintenance using a Digital Twin.

Short Text:

Discrete event simulation of construction activities by using Digital Twin data for productive, resource-efficient, and safe construction planning.

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Finished

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Author:

Eser Senturk (Technische Universität Berlin), Mary Lidiya Kennedy (Technische Universität Berlin)

Introduction:

This document focuses on real-time discrete event simulation (DES) of processes during the construction phase. Real-time Discrete Event Simulation enables the simulation of construction site activities and the evaluation of their impacts on performance indicators (PIs) for productive, resource-efficient, and safe construction works. In close alignment with demonstration cases, work process patterns were determined to develop Discrete Event Simulation mechanism models. Discrete Event System Specification (DEVS) formalisms were created to build a basis for semantic understanding of each Discrete Event Simulation model. The Discrete Event Simulation mechanisms can account for supply-chain logistical, resource-dependent, and spatial characteristics of the site and can use real-time Digital Twin data generated by sensors for predicting future construction works.

1.2 Imprint:

Project Group:

TUB

Partners:

Manuel Jungmann (Technische Universität Berlin), Timo Hartmann (Technische Universität Berlin)

Handling (can be edited based on preference):

Funded by
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Section 2: Use-Case Definition

2.1 Data Sheets & Standards

N/A

2.2 General Definition of the Use-Case

USE CASE DESCRIPTION	
Title	Simulation of Construction Activities Use Case
Goal	Reaching higher efficiencies for productivity, resource efficiency and safety for the real-world construction processes by digital twin supported simulation
Description	To test different construction possibilities in a virtual environment by changing supply chain logistics, resource allocations, and site layouts according to the respective construction site data.
Input Data	The inputs and outputs of the use case depend on the demonstration project. For each demonstration project, there are different construction site activities. Real-time data of these activities are collected from the construction site and used as input data.
Sequence of actions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stochastic probability modeling (this is outside of the use case but it must be always done. It might be integrated into another use case) 2. Enter Input (Probability Density Functions, Active Working Time and Idle Time, Activity Durations, Capacity of Machinery etc.) 3. Data-Driven Discrete Event Simulation 4. Monte-Carlo Simulation 5. Key Performance Indicators Calculation
Primary actors	Project Managers, Civil Engineers, Civil Engineering Companies
Secondary actors	Planning Engineers
Pre-conditions	Adequate amount of production data of the site
Trigger	Development of data based scenarios for predictive site planning
Post-conditions	
Frequency of use	Every day
Support planned for	ASHVIN

UC Created by	
Date of last update	

Figure 1 Use Case Description

Aim and Scope:

The proposed use case aims to present the end-user with more efficient construction planning scenarios based on the real-time data monitoring of the construction sites to find more realistic construction planning information.

Objectives:

This document is developed for the explanation of the simulation of construction processes to achieve more productive construction plans. Stochastic digital twin data of equipment movements are collected by Internet of Things sensors on construction sites. These data are evaluated to gather information about the duration of activities. These data generally represent the current construction site better when it is compared the older planning method which use the data from past construction sites. Thus, more reliable forecasts about the duration of construction processes are enabled and, overall, the whole construction process can be planned enhanced by (micro) discrete event simulation. Typical construction patterns can be combined in a modular approach for easy application of the Simulation of Construction Activities use case. It is only needed to fill in the duration of activities, which is calculated due to the data collection. Subsequently, it is possible to compare different construction possibilities. The allocation of resources and the material supply can be optimized to increase the utilization rate of the equipment. Furthermore, it is possible to enable to coordinate construction works to avoid hazardous situations to reduce the number of accidents. Furthermore, due to the data collection of digital twin data in (near) real-time it is facilitated to track and control the construction process within the Simulation of Construction Activities use case. Hence, if deviations from the planned construction sequence occur, these are much faster identifiable by construction managers and in the following the construction managers can react faster to prevent further losses in the construction process. The Simulation of Construction Activities use case can suggest executing other construction activities, which are not affected by the reason of the deviation.

For stochastic Discrete Event Simulation, Probability Density Functions (PDFs) have to be provided as activity duration inputs. PDFs can be described as real-valued distributions of continuous variables. Probability distributions have different shapes and are described by appropriate parameters. Each continuous probability distribution can take an infinite number of possible values, but according to the PDF, a likelihood is provided that a variate falls within a certain range of values.

Probability density estimation is the procedure to determine suitable PDFs according to sample data. As possible PDFs never represent data exactly, the most suitable PDF has to be determined. For each possible distribution, the corresponding parameters have to be determined by maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) according to independent and identically distributed sample data.

This document provides the developed procedure for real-time Discrete Event Simulation of construction processes and the application of the modeled formalisms. Hence, this report aims to promote the use of digitalization and real-time data in the construction phase. The target audience for this deliverable consists of research and development (R&D) interested parties, professionals from the Architectural Engineering and Construction (AEC) sector, and software developers, who plan to apply the digital twin construction (DTC) paradigm – the proactive management of ongoing construction production based on Digital Twin usage – in the future for construction management. Additionally, it is aimed at informing project managers, construction companies, and public stakeholders about the possibilities of real-time data and the Digital Twin concept. This counts as well for small and medium-sized companies, which possibly do not have the resources for comprehensive R&D activities. Overall, the purpose of this document is to increase understanding and awareness of digitalisation and Digital Twins in the construction phase. Thus, this work provides an incentive for public and private construction and tech companies to initiate a digitalized transformation in the AEC sector.

This use case can be used to divide the construction site into different workspaces according to a location breakdown structure. For each workspace, the needed information such as material quantity or constraints such as maximum possible activities on a workspace has to be stated. Thus, if planning with different workspaces, several trades can work simultaneously without conflicts on a construction site and execution can be accelerated. Thus, different site layouts and their impacts on the Key Performance Indicators can be compared.

2.3 Overall Process:

The overall process for the Simulation of Construction Activities use case use case is presented in Figure 2. Firstly, construction activities should be chosen and configured. Past construction data, environmental conditions, real time construction site data and probability density functions are collected in a database. From the database, key performance indicators and construction activity durations are sent into the configuration step after a proper process in the database. After these steps, Discrete Event Simulation is started and the results are sent to the visualisation software.

In the end, results are shown with visualisation software. These results can be evaluated easily by choosing the suitable construction option according to the preference. The resulting PIs for each option are listed in the end as a table. Some options have duration advantage, some options have resource efficiency advantage, some options have productivity advantage and some options have cost advantages. The user prefer the necessary option in the end.

If the results do not satisfy the user, the user should go back to the scenario configuration again. During all these activities, the outputs of sensors from construction sites are accumulated into the database.

Figure 2 Process Map

Implementation on #4 Logistics hall construction in Germany

The demonstration site in Rinteln, Germany, is an industrial building with an area of almost 30,000 m² and a height of 12 meters. The building consists of two connected halls and is used for production. The building was mainly constructed of prefabricated components such as concrete columns or sandwich panels.

Due to prefabrication, components are constructed in plants and delivered to construction sites, where they only have to be mounted. This procedure relocates the majority of works from construction site, where several uncertainties, such as changing weather conditions, can occur, to a controlled environment in plants. It is assumed, that the usage of prefabricated components can overcome several shortcomings in current construction practice. However, construction by prefabrication requires a higher demand for planning work. Thus, for this demonstration site, the work process pattern of construction by prefabricated columns was chosen. Timely delivery of prefabricated columns and coordinated delivery intervals are essential for successful construction execution. The prefabricated columns are delivered by trucks. Afterwards, the columns are mounted on their corresponding positions by construction workers and a mobile crane. It is aimed to enable a just in time (JIT) delivery to minimise storage space on construction site and achieve a continuous workflow for all resources.

Within the the use case, several changes can be made in the settings to test different construction options in Figure 3. The total number of columns, the columns per delivery, and the delivery interval must be determined. Additionally, the number and costs of different resources can be changed. It is also possible to modify the Probability Density Functions for the activity durations in the Simulation of Construction Activities use case. Weather forecasts can be included. A risky wind speed boundary and the maximum allowed wind speed are further setting options.

Delivery		Setting		Resources		Setting		Weather		Setting	
Total columns		Number		Construction worker		Number		Weather forecast		Table	
Columns per delivery		Number		Mobile Crane		Number		Risky wind speed		Number	
Delivery interval		PDF/ Number		Maximum cranes		Number		Maximum wind speed		Number	
Activity		Setting		Costs per worker		Number					
Delivery		PDF		Costs per crane		Number					
Mounting		PDF									

Figure 3 Settings for mounting of prefabricated

During the entire construction execution, real-time data were gathered by a high-definition webcam. The camera was fixed next to the construction site and pointed at the site to have a broad overview of construction processes. Time-lapsed images were taken every ten minutes and uploaded via internet on the platform. It was consistently possible to access the images on the platform.

The durations for the activity of mounting columns are based on the time-lapsed images. Therefore, the mounting durations result in ten-minute steps. Overall, two weeks were analyzed. In the first week, 53 columns and in the second week 43 columns were mounted (Figure 4).

Activity	First week durations [minutes]	Second week durations [minutes]
Mounting	20, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 20, 20, 20, 20, 20, 10, 10, 10, 10, 20, 30, 30, 10, 20, 20, 10, 20, 20, 20, 20, 20, 20, 10, 10, 10, 20, 20, 10, 20, 10, 10, 10, 20, 10, 20, 10, 20, 20, 10, 20, 10, 10, 20, 20, 10, 10, 10	20, 20, 30, 20, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 20, 30, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 20, 20, 10, 10, 10, 10, 10, 20, 20, 20, 20, 10, 10, 10, 10, 20, 20, 10, 10, 10, 20, 20, 20, 10, 10, 10, 10

Figure 4 Durations for mounting columns

For the process pattern mounting of prefabricated columns, the productivity rate is calculated by dividing the number of mounted columns by the product of the number of resources and the total construction duration. The productivity rate can be calculated for the mobile cranes and the construction workers separately.

$$Productivity\ rate_{crane} = \frac{Output}{Input} = \frac{Number\ mounted\ columns}{Total\ duration * n_{Crane}}$$

$$Productivity\ rate_{worker} = \frac{Output}{Input} = \frac{Number\ mounted\ columns}{Total\ duration * n_{Worker}}$$

The utilisation rate for the mobile cranes is calculated by adding the active usage time of all cranes up divided by the total duration when they are requested, i.e. the sum of the active and idle time for all machines.

$$Utilisation\ rate_{crane} = \frac{\sum_i^n (Active\ time\ crane_i)}{\sum_i^n (Active\ time\ crane_i + Idle\ time\ crane_i)}$$

The safety factor during the mounting of prefabricated columns considers risky weather conditions. The simulation stops construction operations, if a wind speed of 20 m/s is detected. If the wind speed is in the range of 10 to 19.99 m/s and construction works are executed, the duration is calculated as risk time.

$$\text{Safety factor} = \sum_i^n \text{Active time crane}_i \text{ during risky wind} \\
 \text{if } 10 \text{ m/s} \leq \text{wind speed} < 20 \text{ m/s}$$

The costs for equipment and workers are calculated by multiplying the total duration in hours with the number of different resources and costs for each resource per hour. Resources were construction workers and cranes. Costs of 36.60 €/h (Eurostat 2021) were provided for the construction workers and 100 €/h for the crane according to a discussion with the site manager of the construction company. Supply costs were neglected in the calculation but could be added if preferred.

$$\text{Total costs} = \text{Total duration [h]} * (n_{\text{worker}} * \text{Costs worker/h} + n_{\text{crane}} * \text{Costs crane/h})$$

Different options are prepared for this demonstration project with different numbers of columns per delivery, delivery interval, cranes, and construction workers. For each possible option, the Discrete Event Simulation was repeated 1000 times. The different settings for the construction options are presented in Figure 5.

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3	Option 4
Columns per delivery	2	4	4	8
Delivery interval	60	60	90	60
Number cranes	1	1	2	2
Number construction workers	3	3	6	6

Figure 5 Comparison of possible Probability Density Functions for the delivery of columns

For each possible option, the discrete event simulation (DES) was repeated 1,000 times for the demonstration example number 4 Rinteln. The resulting (performance indicator) PIs for each option are listed in Figure 6. Option 4 leads to the lowest construction duration as more resources are provided in comparison to Option 1 and Option 2. Additionally, Option 4 results in low costs. Only for Option 2 a bit lower cost incurs. The reason is the high resource efficiency for the resources in both options. Hence, no idle time occurs as these two options achieve an efficiency of almost 100 %. According to the Discrete Event Simulation, Option 2 results in higher productivity as fewer resources were provided. Option 3 has the lowest productivity and resource efficiency results. In addition, this option leads to the highest costs. The reason is a suboptimal supply chain as much idle time occurs for the resources. It depends on the project manager which aspects are preferred. If a quick execution is required, a second crane must be used on site and more columns must be supplied per delivery as considered in Option 4. However, if there is no time pressure, Option 2 offers an even more efficient and cheaper alternative. In general, it can be detected that the Simulation of Construction Activities use case

supports planning by optimizing the supply chain and resource allocations for the mounting of columns. The visualization of the model is presented in Figure 7.

PI	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3	Option 4
Duration [min]	2,146	1,155	1,632	626
Productivity _{Worker} [column/wh]	0.65	1.17	0.42	1.06
Productivity _{Crane} [column/wh]	1.94	3.5	1.25	3.18
Resource efficiency _{Crane} [%]	50,87	97.65	34.27	96.70
Total cost [€]	7,553	4,196	11,749	4,616
Safety	0	0	0	0

Figure 6 Results for different options

Figure 7 Visualisation demonstration project #4

Implementation on #5 Kineum office building in Sweden

The high-rise building Kineum is in Gothenburg, Sweden, and has 27 floors with a height of 110 meters. It will be used as an office and hotel building. The whole building has a total floor area of around 30,000 m² and the area for each floor differs between 960 and 1,400 m².

The Kineum building has the same or similar floor plans on many floors and for the finishing works the same activities must be executed on each floor. During finishing works many different trades are working simultaneously on one floor. Therefore, coordination of the different trades is essential for successful execution to avoid timespace conflicts. Because of the repetitive nature of the finishing works and the large size of the floor area, the DT concept can be applied to achieve continuous improvement of ongoing works. A pull planning process according to Lean Construction principles can be applied to the different trades' workflows. Hence, for this demonstration site, the finishing works were chosen as a work process pattern.

Within the Simulation of Construction Activities use case, several settings can be made for the finishing works in Figure 8. For each trade, the number of resources and the average cost per worker have to be stated.

For this demonstration site, no data could be collected. If real-time data can be collected in the future, it will be possible to incorporate them into data-driven PDFs. For such a work process pattern, the recording of images at a certain interval would be expedient. Thus, the processes of different trades can be tracked and possible time-space conflicts among trades can be detected.

Activity	Setting
Dry wall first side	PDF
Ventilation	PDF
Plumbing	PDF
Electricity	PDF
Dry wall second side	PDF
Dry ceiling	PDF
Painting	PDF
Floor	PDF
Door	PDF

Resource	Setting
Dry wall constructor	Number
HVAC	Number
Plumbing	Number
Electrician	Number
Painter	Number
Floor layer	Number
Carpenter	Number
Costs per worker	Number

Workspace	Setting
Number workspaces	Number
Maximum simultaneous works	Number
Size dry walls [i]	Number
Size ceiling [i]	Number
Size painting [i]	Number
Size floor [i]	Number
Doors [i]	Number

Figure 8 Possible settings for finishing activities

For each activity, a normal distribution with no deviation is assumed. The mean duration is calculated by dividing the material quantities by the total activity duration in hours. The provided durations, the material quantities, and the resulting Probability Density Functions (PDFs) are indicated in Figure 9.

Operation	Working duration [hours]	Material	PDF
Dry wall first side	498	2,486 m ²	Normal (0.200, 0)
Ventilation	368	2,486 m ²	Normal (0.148, 0)
Plumbing	70	2,486 m ²	Normal (0.028, 0)
Electricity	70	2,486 m ²	Normal (0.028, 0)
Operation	Working duration [hours]	Material	PDF
Dry wall second side	410	2,486 m ²	Normal (0.165, 0)
Dry ceiling	160	963 m ²	Normal (0.166, 0)
Painting	220	5,272 m ²	Normal (0.042, 0)
Floor	395	1,120 m ²	Normal (0.353, 0)
Doors	120	72 pieces	Normal (1.667, 0)
Total	2,311		

Figure 9 Resulting Probability Density Functions for the finishing work activities

For the demonstration site in Gothenburg, the productivity rates for each trade are calculated during the execution of the finishing works. The productivity rate is calculated for each trade by dividing the material quantity by the total duration each trade is demanded on site multiplied by the number of resources.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Productivity rate trade}_i &= \frac{\text{Output}}{\text{Input}} \\
 &= \frac{\text{Material quantity}_i}{\sum_i^n (\text{Active time trade}_i + \text{Idle time trade}_i) * n_i}
 \end{aligned}$$

As no heavy construction equipment is used for these activities, the resource efficiency is calculated for each trade by dividing the active time through the whole time the trade is demanded on site.

$$\text{Resource efficiency trade}_i = \frac{\sum_i^n (\text{Active time trade}_i)}{\sum_i^n (\text{Active time trade}_i + \text{Idle time trade}_i)}$$

Furthermore, the time is calculated when two or more trades work at the same workspace by:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Duration concurrent trades} &= \sum \text{Duration} \\
 &.\text{if number of trades at a workspace} \geq 2.
 \end{aligned}$$

The total costs are calculated by multiplying the active and idle duration for each trade with the number of resources per trade. For each worker, general costs of 37.30 €/h were provided (Eurostat 2021), yielding daily costs of 298.40 €/day.

$$Total\ costs = \sum_i^n ((Active\ time\ trade_i + Idle\ time\ trade_i) * n\ trade_i) \\ * Costs\ worker/day$$

Different options are prepared for this demonstration project with different numbers of workspaces, dry constructor, HVAC, plumbing, electrician, painter, layer, floor layer, and carpenter. Three different options with different resource allocations and several workspaces are compared in Figure 10.

	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Workspaces	1	3	3
Number dry constructor	4	4	10
Number HVAC	4	4	8
Number plumbing	2	2	1
Number electrician	2	2	1
Number painter	4	4	2
Number floor layer	4	4	5
Number carpenter	2	2	4

Figure 10 Settings for construction options in the use case for demonstration project #4

For Option 1, all trades have a continuous workflow besides the dry constructors, as there is only one workspace. After the dry constructors install the first drywall side, they have to wait for the inner wall installations until they can continue with the second side and the ceiling. Thus, only the dry constructors spend around 33 % of the time waiting and are not used efficiently. For all options, the occurrence of different trades on one workspace was prevented in the Discrete Event Simulation. For Option 2, the whole floor was divided into three workspaces of similar sizes. The resource allocation was not changed. Within the second Option, the total construction duration can be decreased significantly as construction works can be executed simultaneously on several workspaces. The trade dry constructor is used much more efficiently compared to Option 1. However, for the remaining trades, more idle time occurs according to the Discrete Event Simulation. Hence, in Option 3, three workspaces are kept, and the resource allocations were changed. The third option leads to the fastest construction execution and is still the cheapest option due to the overall efficient use of the different workers. All trades have an efficiency of more than 80 %. For some trades, higher efficiencies can be achieved in Option 1. Nevertheless, it has to be considered that this is a forward planning, and deviations from this schedule will occur. Therefore, small buffers in the schedule can be seen as useful to avoid conflicts among different trades. No idle time occurs within Option 3. Only for the second and the third workspace, brief idle times can occur according to the Discrete Event Simulation of Option 3. Overall, it can be stated that continuous workflows can be achieved, and the site is

used more efficiently by the application of the use case. For each activity a certain color is assigned and the different workspaces are marked in the appropriate colors for the duration a trade stays at the location according to the Simulation of Construction Activities use case in Figure 11.

Figure 11 Visualisation of the Discrete Event Simulation results of demonstration project #4

Implementation on #6 Office buildings in Spain

This demonstration site is related to the construction of an office building located in the urban area of Barcelona. The shell construction consists of reinforced concrete with long-spanned slabs. The building is shaped like a U and has seven floors with an area of around 16,524 m². Due to the execution of the works within a dense urban area, the construction site has limited space for equipment and vehicles to deliver the material.

As densification of cities is a current topic, the efficient usage of limited construction space in urban areas is needed. Construction works require the usage of heavy equipment such as cranes. Cranes take a crucial part on construction sites by moving materials and effect project costs and duration significantly (Peng et al. 2018). Due to limited space, the risk of hazardous situations rises as several activities occur simultaneously next to each other with no distance between them. Additionally, there is not much space on the streets as usual traffic takes place and should be interrupted as little as possible. It was detected that the duration between leaving the concrete mixing plant and start of the curing process should not surpass a duration of 1.5 hours, as the quality of concrete decreases afterwards significantly (Lin et al. 2010). Thus, the coordination of material deliveries should be on time to minimise disturbances. Based on these aspects, for this demonstration site, the work process pattern of concrete works executed by a tower crane was chosen. Ready mixed concrete was delivered in certain intervals to the

construction site by trucks. Subsequently, the concrete was poured into formwork by a tower crane. This was a repetitive process until the concrete mixer truck was empty. Subsequently, when the empty concrete mixer truck left, the next truck could arrive to start the repetitive process again.

The number and costs of resources can be changed in the tool, i.e. construction workers, cranes, crane operators, workspaces, and the parking locations for trucks. The Probability Density Functions (PDFs) for each activity must be stated as well. Additional inputs are the total concrete volume, the capacity of the truck, the capacity of the concrete bucket, and the delivery interval. Furthermore, a weather forecast, a risky wind speed boundary, and the maximum allowed wind speed can be entered into the tool in Figure 12.

Delivery		Setting	
Total volume concrete [litres]	Number		
Capacity truck [litres]	Number		
Capacity bucket [litres]	Number		
Delivery interval	PDF / Number		
Operation duration		Setting	
Delivery	PDF		
Filling	PDF		
Lifting up	PDF		
Pouring	PDF		
Lifting down	PDF		

Resources		Setting	
Construction workers	Number		
Cranes	Number		
Crane operators	Number		
Concrete location	Number		
Truck location	Number		
Costs per worker	Number		
Costs per crane	Number		
Weather		Setting	
Weather forecast	Table		
Risky wind speed	Number		
Maximum wind speed	Number		

Figure 12 Settings for concrete pouring by crane activity

At this demonstration site, movement crane data were collected by sensors. Different sensors were mounted on a crane hook during the concrete pouring process. The mounted WTGAHRS2 sensor is a combination of an inertial measurement unit (IMU), a GPS tracker, and a barometer. Thus, three-axis acceleration and velocity by the IMU, longitude/latitude/altitude by the GPS tracker, and height by the barometer could be collected. The combined sensors were connected to an ESP32 microcontroller to send the collected data via internet to the ASHVIN platform or to save it on a memory card. Additionally, the IMU sensor WT901, which has integrated Wi-Fi, was mounted.

Collected movement data of crane operations were analyzed by data mining to extract the durations of each repetition of each operation (Figure 13). For the first truck, each operation was repeated nine times and for the second truck, each operation was repeated eight times, except lifting down, which was repeated only seven times as the concrete process was finished, and the bucket was not lifted down again.

Operation	First truck	Second truck
Filling [seconds]	36, 103, 77, 73, 81, 92, 91, 73, 90	131, 65, 58, 72, 62, 68, 84, 49
Lifting up [seconds]	124, 82, 114, 99, 111, 104, 119, 93, 43	99, 93, 85, 95, 98, 123, 79, 90
Concrete pouring [seconds]	37, 112, 58, 59, 57, 68, 83, 50, 240	89, 33, 30, 65, 42, 26, 337, 72
Lifting down [seconds]	90, 108, 91, 96, 76, 98, 101, 70, 108	84, 76, 99, 110, 99, 101, 105

Figure 13 Concrete pouring activity durations

The productivity rate is calculated by multiplying the number of resources with the total duration as input and the quantity of poured concrete as output. On the one hand, the productivity of cranes is calculated. On the other hand, the productivity of construction workers is investigated.

$$Productivity\ rate_{Crane} = \frac{Output}{Input} = \frac{Quantity\ poured\ concrete}{Total\ duration * n_{Crane}}$$

$$Productivity\ rate_{Worker} = \frac{Output}{Input} = \frac{Quantity\ poured\ concrete}{Total\ duration * n_{Worker}}$$

The utilisation rate of equipment is calculated by the summed usage time of cranes divided by the total duration of planned construction works multiplied by the number of cranes.

$$Utilisation\ rate = \frac{\sum_i^p(Active\ time\ crane_i)}{Total\ duration * n_{Crane}}$$

The safety factor considers wind conditions during crane operations. Hazardous situations can occur, if there is wind during crane operations. Thus, the risk duration is calculated when wind is in the range between 10 to 19.99 m/s according to input weather forecasts and construction works are executed at this time.

$$Safety\ factor = Duration\ risky\ wind\ speed * Activity\ time\ crane\ during\ risky\ wind$$

if $10\ m/s \leq wind\ speed < 20\ m/s$

The personnel costs for equipment and workers were calculated by multiplying the total duration in hours with the number of different resources and costs for each resource per hour. Resources were construction workers, cranes, and crane operators. According to Eurostat (2021) the average cost per construction worker per hour for a construction company in Spain are 22.80 €. The assumed cost for a crane per hour was 85 €. Establishment costs were not considered as these expenses would occur independently of the operation duration.

$$Total\ costs = Total\ duration\ [h] * (n_{Worker} * Costs\ worker/h + n_{Crane} * Costs\ crane/h)$$

Different options are prepared for this demonstration project with different numbers of delivery intervals, cranes, crane operators, and construction workers. In Figure 14, settings for

construction options in the use case for the #4 Barcelona demonstration project. The difference between the options is the delivery interval. In reality, the second truck arrived 115 minutes after the first, which led to an idle time of around one hour for the workers and the crane. Three different options with a delivery interval of 60, 30, and 50 minutes were compared to the real execution.

	Observed	Option 2	Option 3	Option 4
Delivery interval [minutes]	115	60	30	50
Number cranes	1	1	1	1
Number crane operators	1	1	1	1
Number construction workers	4	4	4	4

Figure 14 Settings for construction options in the Simulation of Construction Activities Use case for demonstration project #6

Option 1 leads to significant improvements in comparison to the actual execution as the second truck arrives already after 60 minutes and the idle time for the crane and construction workers can be reduced. Thus, all Performance Indicators are influenced positively. However, idle time still occurs for the resources. After the first truck is empty, a short idle time occurs at around 3,000 seconds. The usage of the crane would look the same as the resources are used in combination. The second Option, a delivery interval of 30 minutes, improves the resource efficiency of the crane and construction workers as they are used 100 % of the time. Hence, it can be stated that no idle time for the resources occurs and continuous workflows can be enabled. However, the trucks accumulate on the streets and congestion arises for 20 to 30 minutes as the second truck arrives early. Option 3, a delivery interval of 50 minutes, has the same resulting PIs as Option 2, besides a few seconds longer construction duration. However, the truck deliveries are better coordinated, and only in some replications a brief overlap of the two trucks occur on the streets. Nevertheless, the resources have continuous workflows. In some replications, there is a brief idle time, which does not influence the PIs negatively. Based on the Simulation of Construction Activities use case a delivery interval of around 50 minutes would optimize the construction execution. All stated Performance Indicators (PI)s would be influenced positively and continuous workflows can be enabled. Nonetheless, congestion on the street can be avoided. The supply chain and the site layout can be improved significantly by applying the use case. Within this example, only the arrival of two trucks was simulated, but if considering a higher demand of concrete for construction, the positive effects will increase. As the exact arrival time is influenced by several factors such as traffic during the delivery and cannot be determined on point, the guideline to arrive 50 minutes after the arrival of the previous truck is a reasonable decision. The results of the chosen construction option are provided as a JSON (Javascript Object Notation) file to the database for visualization in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Visualisation for demonstration project #6

2.4 Disciplines:

*Life cycle stages: Construction stage
Production information and construction*

2.5 Life Cycle Stages:

Production information and construction.

Section 3: Process-definition

*Investigation discipline- risk assessment;
Project Management discipline- cost estimation, proposal preparation, and scheduling*

Section 4: Exchange Requirements

In Figure 16, exchange requirements among tools are shown. Firstly, with the preparation of the data file, the user gives input to the database. From the database, real time and past construction site data are sent. After the configuration process, this data is sent to discrete event simulation and, a data file is created for the visualization which will be shown by the visualisation software.

Figure 16 Exchange Requirements

Section 5: Change Log

This is a section only for changes made after publishing to the front end